

Validation of multi-fidelity urban flow numerical model for innovative air mobility against wind tunnel experiments in two facilities

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ABSTRACT

The secure integration of Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAS) in urban environments highlights the need for precise characterization of wind patterns within realistic complex models. This study evaluates the differences in validation data between two wind tunnels for numerical models that support Urban Air Mobility (UAM). Two independent datasets in a LiDAR/DTM-derived complex urban scenario supply velocity and surface-pressure time-averaged measurements to validate multi-fidelity numerical results. Results show that LES improves the RANS time-averaged velocity results, reducing the normalized root mean square error from 24% to less than 10%, minimizing the maximum local error to 30% and outperforming RANS in over 70% of measurement locations. Although LES resolves unsteady wake structures and downstream peaks in turbulent kinetic energy, the employed numerical setup does not fully reproduce experimental velocity fluctuations. Despite inflow sensitivities and differences in turbulence and blockage ratios, normalized surface pressures are highly reproducible across facilities, also showing strong agreement between experiments and CFD simulations. Flow diagnostics reveal distinct zones with different risk signatures depending on local urban geometry and wake interactions. Areas with high-rise, low-density buildings produce strong shear and increase peak velocity and turbulent kinetic energy, which can create hazardous conditions for UAS operations. Results suggest that future UAM studies should validate numerical turbulence spectra and integral length scales at the inflow to ensure realistic reproduction of facility conditions. The obtained dataset enables follow-up work analyses targeting specific UAS mission requirements.

1. Introduction

As cities continue to densify and with current concerns about air quality [1] and inhabitant comfort [2, 3], Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UAS) are bound to contribute to the development of the decarbonized, sustainable, and energy-efficient Smart City. UAS are expected to become increasingly important in applications related to delivery, security, emergency response, and urban mobility [4]. In this regard, Urban Air Mobility (UAM) promises to revolutionize transport and services in cities in the near future; in fact, the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) forecasts UAM to become a reality within 5 years [5]. The need for UAS secure inclusion in urban environments introduces a new application in the field of wind engineering, as urban wind patterns, characterized by complex flow interactions, are critical for drones, altering their performance and hindering safe operations [6], especially during take-off and landing at vertiports [7]. The current trend poses

an emerging challenge: understanding the velocity and turbulence of actual urban fields to aid UAS in path planning and optimization. Governments are starting to implement regulations that affect the operability of aerial vehicles [8], and are delineating no-fly zones based on environmental constraints, such as acoustic emissions, obstacle proximity, and strong wind gusts [9]. In turn, these restrictions are governed by a building-induced wind speed field and turbulent instabilities, which impose additional power requirements and compromise drone maneuverability [10].

Wind tunnel experiments stand out as the most reliable data acquisition method in the field of wind engineering. However, they are constrained to a limited number of discrete measurement points, which cannot resolve the full spatial variability of urban flows required for precise UAS trajectory optimization [11]. On the other hand, numerical approaches offer a faster and more versatile alternative for UAM applications. Giersch et al. [12] emphasized that pre-computing flow solutions across representative boundary-layer conditions could enable a rapid evaluation of the flight trajectory based on actual meteorological conditions, for which a location-specific analysis must be developed. It can be inferred that failing to consider all relevant wind directions can lead to inadequate designs and potential risks.

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43 To study a representative amount of different wind condi- 100
44 tions, and because each wind direction requires a full inde- 101
45 pendent simulation, computationally affordable but under- 102
46 resolving building-scale turbulence simulations should be 103
47 leveraged against higher-fidelity methods. Many authors 104
48 have investigated the strengths and limitations of differ- 105
49 ent turbulence approaches in urban settings in the field 106
50 of Computational Wind Engineering (CWE), emphasizing 107
51 differences in results using LES and RANS. García-Sánchez 108
52 et al. [13] quantified LES uncertainties and concluded its 109
53 superior capabilities regarding high-turbulent flow predic- 110
54 tions. However, Blocken [14] justified the use of RANS 111
55 simulations for routine calculations given the availability of 112
56 best practice guidelines [15] and their lower computational 113
57 requirements. In terms of time-averaged velocity fields, ac- 114
58 cording to Blocken et al. [16], steady RANS simulations can 115
59 provide accurate results with an error margin of around 10% 116
60 in areas where the amplification factor, that is, the increase in 117
61 local wind speed with respect to the wind speed at the same 118
62 location without buildings, is greater than 1. The RANS 119
63 increase in accuracy with the amplification factor is par- 120
64 ticularly important in high-rise building complexes, where 121
65 wind speeds can amplify up to 150% of the free-stream 122
66 velocity [17] due to strong channeling effects that accelerate 123
67 the wind through narrow urban canyons. In contrast, when 124
68 the amplification factor is less than 1, the accuracy of RANS 125
69 simulations deteriorates significantly due to shortcomings 126
70 of the RANS method in how the averaged scalar velocities 127
71 are defined [18]. Results also indicate an underestimation 128
72 of the wind speed at the windward corners of the building 129
73 and the overestimation of the recirculating flow in the wake 130
74 of the buildings in comparison to the results of wind tunnel 131
75 experiments [19]. 132

76 As aircraft are bound to fly through the turbulent wake 133
77 of buildings [9], urban flow studies applied to UAM require 134
78 accurate characterization of the turbulent field within the 135
79 microscale urban fabric [20]. According to Adkins [21], 136
80 smaller eddies comparable in size to the UAS are of the 137
81 most significant concern for these aircraft. Resolving these 138
82 high-frequency wake effects requires advanced modeling 139
83 techniques [22] due to the inherent unsteadiness of turbulent 140
84 phenomena. It follows that UAM studies tend to employ high 141
85 spatial and temporal resolution, and as Roseman and Argrow 142
86 [23] note, LES is particularly valuable for capturing the flow 143
87 structures that must be quantified for safe UAS operations 144
88 and risk assessment. García-Sánchez et al. [13] also report 145
89 that LES is more accurate than RANS in capturing turbulent 146
90 kinetic energy (k) in 80% of measurement locations. Despite 147
91 proving to have more precise results, studies on inflow un- 148
92 certainties [18, 24] highlight additional difficulties for LES. 149
93 García-Sánchez states that in regions where inflow uncer- 150
94 tainties have a greater effect on the flow, the out-performance 151
95 of LES over RANS in terms of averaged velocity prediction 152
96 drops to 50%. In specific contexts, its high sensitivity to 153
97 inlet conditions and the increased computational cost re- 154
98 quired to resolve subgrid-scale turbulence justifies the use 155
99 of faster and less expensive RANS techniques [16]. With 156

100 hybrid approaches yielding very few successes [18] due to
101 the difficulty of switching between RANS and LES, these
102 conditions underscore the need for a multi-fidelity analysis
103 to assess the effect of turbulence treatment in urban flows.

104 A major limitation across current UAM research frame-
105 works is the scarce collection of experimentally validated
106 urban flow numerical simulations [11, 12]. Risk assess-
107 ments for UAM operations frequently depend on velocity
108 and turbulence fields from RANS simulations; however, the
109 limited validation against wind-tunnel experiments leaves
110 residual uncertainty in safety and performance assessments
111 for UAS operations [25]. Furthermore, comparative wind-
112 tunnel studies have shown that facility-specific factors, such
113 as blockage ratios, incorrect reference static pressure in
114 open-circuit tunnels, or differences in the turbulence inte-
115 gral scale, can produce systematic shifts in mean and peak
116 results [26]. While these discrepancies have been studied
117 in single high-rise buildings, their impact on actual urban
118 environments is yet to be analyzed. Modern drone flight
119 planning optimization tools that rely on high-accuracy CFD
120 wind fields [27] have also been demonstrated on simplified
121 building geometries. Upcoming trajectory planning efforts
122 must expand their scope to more practical and realistic lay-
123 outs. Thus, the current lack of experimental and high-fidelity
124 numerical urban flow datasets represents a significant barrier
125 to both the accurate validation of UAM risk studies and the
126 future application of flight-planning systems to actual urban
127 scenarios.

128 The primary objective of this study is to assess the im-
129 pact of facility-specific differences in wind-tunnel environ-
130 ments on the aerodynamic response of a complex, real-case
131 urban model and to compare those results with CFD predic-
132 tions. To this end, two different wind tunnels have studied
133 the same 1:375-scale mock-up of the authorized UAS flight
134 zone Urban Lab in Benidorm, Spain. These comparisons
135 ensure the calibration of multi-fidelity CFD simulations,
136 which are more suitable for UAM applications, by assessing
137 whether CFD results lie within empirical bounds. As dis-
138 cussed above, a specific, validated urban wind database is
139 needed to apply CFD predictions to wind-aware real-time
140 UAS mission planning [28]. To ensure reproducibility of
141 results, this work compiles all the steps necessary to perform
142 the CFD urban flow study and its experimental validation.
143 To the authors' knowledge, this is one of the first attempts
144 in the literature to perform a cross-validation of experimental
145 results on an actual LiDAR/DTM-derived urban mock-up
146 in two wind tunnels. Furthermore, the present study also
147 contributes to the need to expand the existing urban flow
148 database [29] with a calibrated digital twin of an operational
149 flight zone suitable for on-site drone actuation testing and
150 mission planning.

151 The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Sec-
152 tion 2 describes the two experimental campaigns, including
153 the wind tunnel facilities, boundary layer generation tech-
154 niques, and the field geometry employed, as well as an in-
155 depth description of the data acquisition process. The inflow
156 velocity, turbulence characteristics, and their corresponding

157 results are compared. The numerical methodology is seen in
 158 section 3. This section justifies the computational domain,
 159 mesh generation strategy, boundary conditions (BC), and
 160 turbulence modeling approaches employed in the study.
 161 Section 4 validates the performance of different turbulence
 162 models against experimental data, with a focus on time-
 163 averaged flow characteristics. Finally, the assessment of
 164 wind tunnel effects on experimental results is presented.

165 2. Experimental setup

166 As previously stated, to investigate the effect of wind
 167 tunnel characteristics and assess the reproducibility of the
 168 study, experimental tests were performed in the facilities
 169 of two universities. The first set of experiments was con-
 170 ducted in the ACLA-16 wind tunnel by researchers from
 171 the *Instituto Universitario "Ignacio Da Riva"* (IDR/UPM).
 172 These studies were validated against tests carried out by the
 173 CMT-Clean Mobility & Thermofluids Institute (UPV) in the
 174 *Profesor Francisco Payri* wind tunnel (from now on, the
 175 authors refer to two sets of experiments and their results as
 176 IDR or CMT, respectively). This comparison aims not only
 177 to validate the employed urban flow experimental procedure
 178 but also to highlight key features that might alter the flow
 179 behavior in the region of interest and assess the repeatability
 180 of results. By using the same model in both experiments,
 181 differences in results can be attributed to differences in the
 182 Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL) generators, the wind
 183 tunnel test section, and atmospheric air conditions.

184 2.1. Wind tunnels

185 The IDR ACLA-16 [30], located in the Montegancedo
 186 campus premises of the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid,
 187 is a closed test section, closed circuit wind tunnel that
 188 features a square cross-section, measuring 2.2 m per side,
 189 and an overall length of 20 m, subdivided into a flow-
 190 conditioning chamber and a measurement section. The wind
 191 tunnel is equipped with 16 fans, each with a total power of
 192 7.5 kW, which allows a maximum test velocity of 32 m/s
 193 with a turbulence intensity of approximately 1.8%.

194 On the other hand, the CMT *Profesor Francisco Payri*
 195 [31] open wind tunnel features a working section length of
 196 22 m and a square cross-section with a side length of 2.84
 197 m, trimmed with chamfers at all corners. With nine 45 kW
 198 fans, the wind tunnel has a maximum velocity of around 32.5
 199 m/s and a turbulence intensity of 0.2%. This facility is also
 200 divided into different sections to allow the measurement of
 201 two independent studies.

202 2.2. Atmospheric Boundary Layer configuration

203 Flow conditioning was conducted independently in the
 204 two facilities to reproduce the scaled inflow properties im-
 205 pinging on the model with the real ABL profile developed
 206 over Benidorm. This profile is influenced by the effect of
 207 obstacles surrounding the measurement region. Depending
 208 on the average roughness of these obstacles, the European
 209 wind standard specifies five different types of terrain [32],

210 which describe a logarithmic velocity and turbulence inten-
 211 sity profiles. The Eurocode 1 [32] establishes a neutral strat-
 212 ification approach to tackle urban airflow analyses, which
 213 defines the dominant behavior of neutral ABLs by assuming
 214 a null mean vertical wind speed [12]. In that sense, studies
 215 on the effect of thermal effects, which usually create vertical
 216 instabilities in the wind profile, revealed that thermally-
 217 generated turbulence is secondary compared to mechanical
 218 effects [21]. Furthermore, an approach that neglects thermal
 219 buoyancy effects has been successfully applied in similar
 220 studies [13, 33, 34]. Due to the terrain's orography and the
 221 Urban Lab's characteristics, a Eurocode 1 terrain Category
 222 III was targeted by both wind tunnels. The velocity profile
 223 has been approximated by a power law as per the ASCE 7
 224 [35] Category C, $u = C \cdot z^\alpha$, where C is an arbitrary constant
 225 and $\alpha = 0.2$.

226 ABL generator setups can typically be divided into
 227 spires, which primarily increase the turbulence intensity
 228 of the flow, and subsequent surface roughness elements,
 229 which reduce the velocity of the flow near the ground to
 230 create the ABL. Due to the different placement of the model
 231 within the wind tunnel and especially the disparity in cross-
 232 sections and turbulence characteristics of the flow, a different
 233 turbulence generator layout is designed to transform the
 234 uniform-velocity incident flow into the desired ABL for each
 235 wind tunnel. The two configurations used in this paper can
 236 be seen in Figure 1. The available test section of the IDR set
 237 of experiments allows for a more gradual transition of the
 238 velocity profile: the IDR experiment incorporates different
 239 sizes of cubic roughness elements, ranging from 150 to 70
 240 mm per side. The assembly also includes a 300 mm height
 241 barrier and 220×1930 mm triangular spires in base width
 242 (w) and height (h), respectively. Conversely, CMT's set of
 243 experiments uses 65×90×90 mm rectangular blocks and
 244 180×1420 mm $w \times h$ spires. Main features are gathered in
 245 Table 1.

246 A comparison of normalized vertical wind profiles for
 247 the two tests against the Eurocode Type III ABL profile
 248 is presented in Figure 2, along with the normalized root
 249 mean square error (NRMSE) values calculated in the region
 250 of interest, that is, the airspace that typically limits UAV
 251 flights, from 20 to 120 m in height [10]. Due to the dif-
 252 ference in absolute velocity between the two experiments,
 253 non-dimensional vertical profiles are expressed with respect
 254 to an arbitrary $z_{ref} = 60$ m. The NRMSE values of the
 255 streamwise velocity are calculated according to the follow-
 256 ing equation:

$$257 \text{NRMSE} = \frac{\text{RMSE}}{\phi_{ref}} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\phi_i - \phi_i^{ref})^2}}{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \phi_i^{ref}}, \quad (1)$$

258 where ϕ^{ref} represents the reference Eurocode profile. NRMSE
 259 results indicate a good agreement with the Eurocode ref-
 260 erence, with the boundary-layer thickness (~ 0.40 m at
 261 model scale) matching the reference Eurocode 1 Type III
 262 within $\pm 5\%$ error. Experiments show a greater difficulty in
 matching the intensity profile of the Eurocode. A maximum

Figure 1: Effective test sections for IDR (top) and CMT (bottom) wind tunnels and ABL turbulence generator setups

2.3. Field geometry description and mock-up

The study focuses on a designated UAS flight zone of the city of Benidorm, shown in Figure 3. The geometry used in this study is a simplification of the landscape and urban fabric of a 350-meter-radius circular domain around the UAS flight zone. Note that significant discrepancies in measurement points can usually be attributed to geometry simplifications [19, 37]. In this case, obstacles below a height of 6 m were removed, while maintaining only relevant buildings that influence the overall flow behavior. To reconstruct the geometry of the buildings and the terrain, high-resolution geospatial data were obtained from open-access cartographic databases. The building perimeters were downloaded as vector layers (Shapefile format) from the Electronic Office of the Spanish Cadaster [38]. The raster files corresponding to the Digital Terrain Model (DTM) [39] and the Normalized Digital Surface Model of Buildings (nDSM) [40], both with a 1-meter mesh spacing, were obtained from the Valencian Spatial Data Infrastructure (IDEV). The DTM contained the absolute terrain elevations, while the nDSM provided the height of the buildings relative to the ground. Using ArcGIS Pro software [41], both digital models were combined through map algebra, thereby generating a model of the rooftop elevations. Maximum building height values were extracted using the cadastral footprint as a mask. This information enabled the interpolation and extrusion of the 3D building volumes, resulting in an accurate representation of the urban morphology. Additionally, to further increase the geometric fidelity of the model, a simplified representation of the terrain relief was generated using 6-meter elevation contour lines extracted from the DTM, which were simplified and transformed into vector polygons to represent the stepped elevation layers, later used in the topographic model. The final geometry of the city is seen in Figure 4.

To ensure compatibility with the available wind tunnel facilities, the experimental model was built at a scale of 1:375. This scale was selected to maximize the model size within the constraints of the test section while preserving the dominant flow features of interest. Therefore, the blockage ratio inside the wind tunnel test chambers is less than 5%. Moreover, for bluff-body dominated urban flows, the Reynolds number (Re) independence of the wake characteristics allows for reliable extrapolation of results from scaled models [42], so long as the Re satisfies a critical threshold dependent on the roughness Reynolds number, Re_{z_0} , and the dimensionless height, z_+ [43]. This assumption is commonly accepted in urban wind engineering and supports the use of reduced-scale models for aerodynamic studies [44]. Taking into account the velocity profile and the main geometric properties of the buildings, the Re of the model, defined as

$$Re = \frac{U l}{\nu} \quad (2)$$

where U is the wind speed, l is the building width, and ν is the air kinematic viscosity, lies between $2 \cdot 10^4$ and $6 \cdot 10^4$ in the area of interest. Hence, this experimental setup ensures a wind speed-independent flow regime, as this range is above

NRMSE of 20% can be seen in Figure 2. This error, however, falls within reasonable margins [36], especially considering the building-induced dominant turbulent flow regime that occurs after the first line of buildings.

Figure 2: ABL velocity (left) and turbulence intensity (right) comparison. $z_{ref} = 60$ m. The NRMSE with respect to the Eurocode Type III profiles is seen in parentheses

Figure 3: Aerial view of Benidorm city. The North direction corresponds to the upward direction. The authorized flight area for UAS is highlighted in red

321 the critical $Re_{crit} = 1.1 \cdot 10^4$ recommended for building wind
 322 tunnel testing [44].

323 A flush-mounted rotating platform accommodates the
 324 scale model and allows for accurate orientation at different
 325 angles of incidence. Based on the wind rose of Benidorm
 326 city, this work analyzes the two principal wind directions:
 327 N-S (or $\beta = 0^\circ$), and S-N (or $\beta = 180^\circ$). The asymmetric
 328 orography of the terrain forces an elevation between the
 329 wind tunnel's floor and the model's ground. In turn, this step
 330 introduces a detachment of the flow in the model, which
 331 would alter the ABL velocity and turbulence profiles from
 332 their actual behavior. To mitigate the impact of the step
 333 and ensure a smooth transition between the ABL generation
 334 zone and the urban model, two transition ramps are included
 335 on each side of the city in the experimental and numerical
 336 analyses. A parametric numerical study of the ramp geom-
 337 etry revealed that steep slope angles introduce a contraction
 338 in the cross-section, accelerating the flow and inducing a
 339 contraction of the ABL thickness. Nevertheless, the ramps of
 340 both studies—between 1° and 3.5° , depending on the facility
 341 and the angle of incidence of the flow—do not significantly
 342 alter the dimensionless behavior of the ABL [45].

343 2.4. Instrumentation and data acquisition

344 In IDR's set of experiments, surface pressure has been
 345 recorded via 294 taps (24 buildings instrumented + 15 Irwin
 346 probes) connected to 5 Scanivalve ZOC 33/64Px2 sen-
 347 sors, ± 10 in H_2O (2488 Pa) full scale range, and ± 0.15 % full
 348 scale accuracy. The sampling has been performed at 150 Hz
 349 sampling rate for a 120 s time period. A Pitot tube mounted
 350 outside of the boundary layer and any wake-interference
 351 position has provided the reference dynamic pressure for
 352 c_p computation. Hot-wire anemometry (Dantec 55P91) has
 353 been used to measure the three velocity components at 21
 354 heights per probe location up to 0.42 m for $\beta = 0^\circ$ and
 355 $\beta = 180^\circ$, with sampling at 5 kHz for 104 s. Furthermore,

Figure 4: Mock-up of a selected region of Benidorm city scaled 1:375. Buildings in gray are not instrumented. Kronos building is painted black as a reference

the Irwin probes [46], each consisting of two pressure taps 356
 separated by 1 cm in the vertical direction, have been used to 357
 calculate wind velocity close to the ground. These data yield 358
 both mean and turbulent fluctuations for direct validation of 359
 CFD velocity fields and turbulence statistics. 360

CMT's set of experiments consisted of a total of 124 361
 pressure taps, measured using a Chell microDAQ3 pressure 362
 scanner. This instrument offers a maximum absolute range of 363
 0.5 kPa to 400 kPa, with an error of 0.02%. The sampling 364
 frequency was 400 Hz for a 120-second time period. Al- 365
 though a Pitot tube was used to characterize the ABL, these 366
 tests only included pressure measurements in the mock-up. 367
 Differences in the acquisition process can be seen in Table 1. 368

To help understand the measurements across the study, 369
 the top view of the model is displayed in Figure 5. The 370
 buildings instrumented with pressure probes are depicted in 371

Table 1
Comparison of experimental setup characteristics in both wind tunnels

Category	Parameter	IDR	CMT
Wind tunnel facilities	Cross-section [m]	2.2 × 2.2	2.8 × 2.8, chamfered
	Length [m]	20	22
ABL generation setup	Spire ($w \times h$) [mm]	220 × 1930	180 × 1420
	Roughness elements dimensions [mm]	150 to 70 per side	65 × 90 × 90
	Barrier height [mm]	300	–
	Upstream development region [m]	11.1	8.6
Instrumentation	Velocity measurement method	Hot-wire anemometry	–
	Velocity probe sensor	Dantec 55P91	–
	Velocity sampling frequency [Hz]	5000	–
	Pressure scanner	Scanivalve ZOC 33/64PxX2	Chell microDAQ3
	Number of pressure taps	294	124
Experimental notes	Pressure sampling frequency [Hz]	150	400
	p_{amb} [Pa]	92695	101997
	Measurement time [s]	120	120

372 blue, surrounding the UAS airspace outlined in red. Colored
 373 dots locate the position of velocity probes: red and black
 374 dots represent hot-wire vertical measurement line locations
 375 for $\beta = 0^\circ$ and $\beta = 180^\circ$, respectively, while green dots
 376 highlight the ground measurement position for Irwin probes.

Figure 5: Top view of the city model. In blue, instrumented buildings. Black and red dots represent hot-wire measurement positions for $\beta = 0^\circ$ and $\beta = 180^\circ$, respectively. Green dots indicate the location of Irwin probes

377 3. Numerical setup

378 The numerical calculations were performed on UPV’s
 379 “Sirius” cluster using the commercial software Star-CCM+
 380 (v19.04.007). Both LES and RANS simulations have assumed
 381 incompressible flow, given the low Mach number of the flow.
 382 The following sections describe the computational domain and mesh,
 383 the BC, and the numerical settings for

both stationary and unsteady simulations. Then, the resolution of the LES setup assesses the reach of high-fidelity simulations to capture turbulent phenomena.

3.1. Computational domain and mesh

The computational domain has been selected to replicate IDR’s experimental procedure and is seen in Figure 6. Numerical simulations replicate IDR’s experiment because they are more suitable for UAM studies, given the availability of both pressure and velocity probes, which provide more information regarding the flow mean and fluctuating velocity that may affect UAS operations. In this type of study, it is common to create a domain that is sufficiently large to avoid disturbing the flow around the buildings [17]. This time, however, the selected domain replicates the dimensions of the wind tunnel, a procedure successfully employed by the AIJ [19], as this would provide a more accurate assessment of the influence of the walls in the model flow measurements. As described in subsection 2.1, the IDR’s wind tunnel domain presents a square section with a width of 2.2 m, with the city centered on the floor. The length of the wind tunnel has been shortened upstream of the city to match the inlet of the simulations with the ABL experimental measurement line, thereby avoiding the need for an ABL conditioning region and saving computational costs. In total, the domain extends 4.7 m upstream of the model and 15 m downstream of it.

The meshing strategy employs Star-CCM+’s trimmed mesher algorithm [47] to generate a predominantly hexahedral grid. As shown in Figure 6, the mesh is progressively refined within a dedicated refinement region enclosing the urban model, ensuring increased spatial resolution in areas of complex flow development. Other refinement areas, as characterized in Table 2, include the ground, the other wind tunnel walls, and the city, with its building wakes. This method yields better results for complex geometries [48] and ensures a smooth transition between coarse and fine cells, which facilitates the convergence of the simulations.

Figure 6: Domain close-up and differentiated mesh refinement areas: ground, city, and wind tunnel (WT) walls. The mid plane displays the mesh refinement region and cell distribution around buildings

Table 2

Mesh parameter description. $H_{ref} = 0.7$ m for RANS and $H_{ref} = 0.45$ for LES

Parameter	Domain	Wind tunnel walls	Ground	Refinement region	City
Cell size (% of H_{ref})	20	6.25	1.56	2.21	0.78
Number of PL	–	5	7	7	7
PL thickness (% of H_{ref}) (RANS/LES)	–	5.7/2.22	3.6/1.11	1.4/1.11	1.4/0.44
Wake size [m]	–	–	–	–	0.3

420 Research studies such as Murakami's [49] have stressed
 421 the difficulty of flow modeling around bluff-body sharp
 422 edges, characterized by the anisotropic distribution of the
 423 strain-rate tensor. Based on guidelines for RANS simulations
 424 regarding the minimum number of cells per building face
 425 [50, 51, 52], the cell size was chosen to target at least ten
 426 cells on each side of a building to accurately capture flow
 427 separation around the upwind corners. RANS simulations
 428 also cluster an average of 5 cells within the first 1.5 m
 429 above the ground, which satisfies AIJ's guidelines that recom-
 430 mend a minimum of 3-4 cells in this region [15]. For
 431 LES simulations, the described grid resolution is increased
 432 to resolve smaller turbulence scales. Both grids are described
 433 in Table 2, where $H_{ref} = 0.7$ m for RANS and $H_{ref} = 0.45$
 434 for LES.

435 The employed boundary layer refinements (see Table 2)
 436 yield an average $y^+ = 0.95$ in the region of interest, with
 437 96.6% of elements exhibiting a $y^+ < 2$. The resulting grid
 438 used for RANS simulations, chosen after conducting a mesh
 439 independence study, has approximately 12.8 million cells
 440 and is shown in Figure 7. On the contrary, the LES grid
 441 was obtained by reducing the RANS grid's base cell size,
 442 resulting in a mesh of 59.6 million cells. The quality metrics
 443 employed to ensure that the grid resolution is sufficient to
 444 resolve the relevant flow structures are described in subsec-
 445 tion 3.4.

Figure 7: Mesh zoom-in of the building region. Surface elements and fluid cells are painted in black and red, respectively

3.2. Boundary Conditions

446 García-Sánchez et al. [13] state the challenge of defining
 447 precise BC in LES simulations. The primary difficulty lies in
 448 defining fluctuating inlet conditions that reproduce both the
 449 time-averaged and turbulent characteristics of the velocity
 450 field. In fact, uncertainty related to the inflow conditions
 451 can decrease the accuracy of high-fidelity simulations [13].
 452 Regarding inflow BCs, Tominaga [18] establishes different
 453 approaches to replicate wind tunnel experiments. In contrast
 454 to precursor and recycling approaches, which require mod-
 455 eling the entire wind tunnel domain to predict the ABL de-
 456 velopment, the Synthetic Eddy Method (SEM) [53] applied
 457 in this study introduces turbulent structures directly at the
 458 inlet. To define the inflow ABL profile, experimental data
 459

are required for the mean velocity distribution, Reynolds stresses, and integral length scale. Synthetic eddies then develop over the terrain, replicating the mean flow and fluctuation characteristics of the experimental measurements. This approach eliminates the need for precursor domains and associated turbulence-generation regions, thereby reducing computational costs.

In the present LES setup, turbulent statistics have been derived from wind tunnel measurements of streamwise (u) and vertical (w) velocity components. The transversal component has been statistically approximated by assuming its variance is equal to that of the vertical component. The choice is physically consistent with the lower order of magnitude of vertical fluctuations relative to the streamwise component, providing a conservative estimate for the k . Moreover, García-Sánchez et al. [13] emphasize that uncertainties in the inflow turbulence decay downstream, where local turbulence is primarily governed by canopy-scale shear and building interactions. The integral time scale, $\tau_u(z)$, has been obtained by integrating the normalized autocorrelation of u' up to its first zero crossing. Then, the length scale (L_u) was computed using Taylor's frozen turbulence hypothesis, following Equation 3.2.

$$L_u = u \cdot \tau_u \quad (3)$$

For the RANS simulations, turbulence quantities have been defined in accordance with standard practice and the AIJ guidelines [15]. The k was determined from the measured RMS of velocity fluctuations, σ , using equation Equation 3.2. The dissipation rate ϵ was estimated assuming local equilibrium of the production term P_k in the k equation and using the Boussinesq approximation, leading to the expression seen in Equation 3.2, where U is the vertical velocity profile, and C_μ is the model constant ($= 0.09$)[15].

$$k(z) = \frac{\sigma_u^2 + \sigma_v^2 + \sigma_w^2}{2} \simeq \sigma_u^2 \quad (4)$$

$$\epsilon(z) \simeq C_\mu^{1/2} \cdot k \cdot \frac{dU(z)}{dz} \quad (5)$$

All solid boundaries were treated as no-slip walls. This replicates the physical test-section confinement: the wind tunnel walls and building faces were modeled as smooth walls with low-Reynolds treatment near the wall. The outlet is configured as a zero-gradient, constant-pressure boundary.

3.3. Solver settings

The steady model has been employed when using Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) equations with the realizable k - ϵ turbulence model, which is seen to provide more accurate results in the AIJ's CWE benchmark [19]. Near-wall treatment resolves the viscous sublayer, with the first layer $y^+ \approx 1$ in the city region, thereby capturing the near-wall velocity gradient and turbulence production explicitly rather than relying on wall functions. Resolving the near-wall velocity profile also improves the prediction of wall pressure coefficients (c_p), which are used to compare the two

experimental studies. While this work, due to the 1:375 scale of the model, resolves the viscous sublayer with a y^+ around 1 in the region of interest, it is worth noting that this would not be possible with a real scale factor, and wall functions would be required [13]. RANS simulations have employed a segregated solver with SIMPLE pressure-velocity coupling and second-order convection schemes for both momentum and turbulence equations.

Unsteady, scale-resolving simulations have used LES with the Wall-Adapting Local Eddy-viscosity (WALE) subgrid-scale model [54]. The WALE model assumes a mixing-length type equation for the subgrid scale viscosity and is less dependent on the value of the model coefficient, C_w [55]. The WALE model has been chosen because it provides correct near-wall scaling for the eddy viscosity without requiring a dynamic procedure, making it robust for complex, wall-bounded urban geometries. A bounded-central differencing scheme has been used for the spatial discretization, while second-order implicit schemes have been applied for temporal discretization. LES simulations have been run with a global time step of $\Delta t = 2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ s, matching the experimental velocity sampling frequency. The simulations have been run for a total time of $3s \simeq 55\tau_{conv}$, where τ_{conv} represents the convective time of LES simulations, based on the maximum height of the buildings (0.4 m) and the free-flow velocity of approximately 7.4 m/s. This interval provides a meaningful sampling period for turbulent statistics, consistent with the amount of time scales utilized in previous LES urban studies [13].

All simulations were performed on UPV's "Sirius" high-performance computer cluster, equipped with Intel Xeon 8480 56-core processors. Each RANS case required between 6 and 8 hours of wall time to converge, corresponding to approximately 100 CPU hours per run. In contrast, each LES simulation required approximately 67 wall-clock hours, nearly 45 000 CPU hours per case. LES simulations employed six compute nodes, each with 112 cores.

3.4. LES mesh quality assessment

The adequacy of the LES spatial resolution has been verified by the k ratio, which assesses the accurate prediction of the energy content of turbulent structures. The k ratio η , described in Equation 3.4, is applicable for almost any complex flow and has been successfully used in bluff-body studies [55]. It relates the ratio of the k of the calculated non-filtered eddies, k_c , and the kinetic energy introduced by the subgrid-scale model, k_{SGS} . The higher the ratio, the closer the solution is to a Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS) resolution ($\eta = 1$); according to Torregrosa et al. [55], a correct resolution of a LES can be assumed from $\eta > 0.7$. Values of η below this threshold in areas with high turbulence indicate increased sensitivity to the SGS closure and grid resolution, leading to errors in the wake and recirculation regions.

$$\eta = \frac{k_c}{k_{TOTAL}} = \frac{k_c}{k_{SGS} + k_c} \quad (6)$$

561 The distribution of η (expressed as a percentage) across
 562 the urban domain is mapped in Figure 8. More than 99.5% of
 563 the cells in the city region exhibit a k ratio higher than 80%,
 564 indicating that the bulk of the domain is well resolved with
 565 the used grid. A scarce group of cells present ratios below
 566 70%, but they only cluster near building corners and sep-
 567 aration regions, especially at high-rise and windward first-
 568 line buildings. In the first-row buildings, the high-velocity
 569 inflow (high local Re) ABL meets sharp building edges, thus
 570 combining strong local production P_k with thin shear layers.
 571 Linear shear-layer theory predicts that the most unstable
 572 Kelvin–Helmholtz modes produce eddies with wavelength
 573 on the order of the shear-layer thickness, δ , thereby shifting
 574 the dominant energy-containing scales and the dissipation
 575 range toward smaller scales. This explains the lower values
 576 of η in these areas for a given LES filter width, which is
 577 proportional to cell size. High-rise buildings suffer similar
 578 effects; as Roth [56] notes, the flow above the urban canopy
 579 behaves like a mixing layer between the slower within-
 580 canopy flow and the faster above-canopy wind, which ex-
 581 plains why roof-level high shear is produced. Downstream of
 582 the first row, the interaction between shear-generated eddies
 583 mixes the flow, increasing the integral scale. As the grid
 584 filter is maintained, a larger fraction of the energy-containing
 585 motions is resolved rather than modeled.

586 Given that the low-resolution cells constitute a very
 587 small fraction of the domain and are confined to geometri-
 588 cally singular regions, the present grid was deemed accept-
 589 able for the objectives of this study. Since the small-scale
 590 energy they generate tends to dissipate downstream, these
 591 cells make a negligible contribution to field mean metrics.
 592 Furthermore, a refinement based on η in those localized
 593 regions would reduce the SGS share but at a substantially
 594 higher computational cost.

Figure 8: Calculated (k_c) over total ($k_c + k_{SGS}$) k ratio (η) at plane $z = 0.1$ m (37.5 m full-scale height). Cells with k ratio ($\eta < 0.7$) are highlighted in black

4. Results and discussions

In this section, experimental data are compared with RANS and LES results, highlighting errors in the numerical approach and the shortcomings of different turbulence models. The analysis of results focuses on the time-averaged velocity (subsubsection 4.1.1) and k field (subsubsection 4.1.2), as these variables are most relevant for UAS flight performance and stability. Since velocity measurements are only available from IDR's experiments, these data are compared with the corresponding numerical predictions. As explained in subsection 2.4, these comparisons include velocity measurements in vertical probes for $\beta = 0^\circ$ and $\beta = 180^\circ$, although comparisons between CFD and wind tunnel results are only displayed for $\beta = 0^\circ$ to avoid repetition. Furthermore, the time-averaged c_p shown in subsubsection 4.1.3 provides a complementary measure of numerical accuracy. Finally, the reproducibility of experimental results is discussed in subsection 4.2 by comparing the c_p distribution measured in Benidorm's Urban Lab across the two wind tunnels.

4.1. Experimental validation of RANS and LES time-averaged flow fields

4.1.1. Comparison of mean velocity field

The normalized mean velocity field with respect to the inflow velocity at a representative 37.5 m full-scaled height is shown in Figure 9. The relation between local velocity and the unperturbed inflow velocity is defined as the amplification factor [16], and directly affects numerical accuracy. Both numerical approaches reproduce the general flow trends; however, RANS underpredicts velocity within the wake region of all buildings, where smaller amplification factor values are obtained. As Leitl et al. [57] suggested, the inherent steadiness of the RANS provokes fewer turbulence structures close to the walls. In turn, less turbulence mixing is produced, resulting in an overestimation of the detached flow in the wake of the buildings. This not only affects the velocity of the wake region but also induces error in the reattachment point of the flow. While RANS usually matches LES results for amplification factors greater than 1, the absence of vortex shedding also explains the overestimation of mean velocities in flow acceleration corridors, where actual flow intermittently accelerates due to shear-layer instabilities rather than sustained channeling.

The flow downstream of buildings exhibits different behavior depending on local geometry and wake interactions. Atzori et al. [58] studied flow past simple tandem-obstacle configurations and identified three distinct flow regimes for different building separations. As the separation distance increases, the flow regime is characterized by skimming, where the shear layer passes directly over both obstacles with limited penetration between them, by wake interference of the upstream obstacle with the front face of the downstream one, and finally by an independent wake with minimal interaction. As shown in Figure 9, in this case, flow patterns are influenced by the interaction among multiple obstacles,

Figure 9: Contours of the time-averaged velocity magnitude relative to the inflow velocity, U_{in} . Results from RANS (left) and LES (right) at $z = 0.1$ m (37.5 m full-scale) for $\beta = 0^\circ$ (N-S wind)

650 producing locally accelerated jets and asymmetric recirculation
 651 zones. This indicates that the characteristic flow regime
 652 of complex urban geometries cannot be classified under a
 653 single transition, but rather results from the superposition
 654 of multiple interacting shear layers. The high recirculation
 655 behavior is predominant to the west of the Urban Lab, an
 656 area dominated by low-rise, densely packed buildings. In
 657 contrast, the Urban Lab presents high-rise, widely spaced
 658 buildings, which allow flow penetration and partial recovery
 659 of the streamwise momentum. This region also exhibits more
 660 abrupt flow accelerations in the separation regions. This
 661 conclusion is consistent with simplified geometries; Tominaga
 662 and Shirzadi [59] also reported that the presence of high-rise
 663 buildings increases peak wind speeds relative to the mean
 664 wind speed. The complexity of the flow also highlights urban
 665 features that may create hazardous conditions for UAM.
 666 For example, high wind gust regions are formed due to the
 667 contraction of sections between buildings, and intricate
 668 flow patterns develop in street canyons. In practical terms,
 669 sudden changes in wind direction can potentially hinder
 670 UAS operations, as they can displace UAS from their flight
 671 paths, leading to a loss of control or collision with nearby
 672 structures [23].

673 The correlation between numerical and experimental
 674 wind speed ratios is seen in Figure 10, with RMSE calculated
 675 using Equation 2.2. Non-dimensional velocities represent
 676 the ratio between the velocity and the inflow velocity of
 677 the ABL at a reference height $z_{ref} = 60$ m, in accordance
 678 with a representative UAS flight height. The calibration
 679 plot shows that the mean velocity distributions are broadly
 680 consistent with the experimental wind tunnel data, particu-
 681 larly in regions where the flow remains relatively stable.
 682 Steady RANS models exhibit an averaged error of 24.9%,

which increases significantly in strong recirculation regions,
 where local errors can exceed 80%. Despite the inherent
 increase in computational cost, LES performs better in
 predicting the mean velocity field. The LES results represent
 the experimental trend with an average error within 10%.
 In the current numerical configuration, LES outperforms
 RANS in over 70% of locations, with a maximum local
 error of 30% compared to experimental data. Overall, the
 results suggest that, for specific applications, UAM studies
 may combine RANS simulations fine-tuned with LES to
 characterize mean velocity fields across a wide range of
 operating conditions.

Figure 10: Velocity magnitude calibration plot for CFD and IDR's experimental data. $U_{ref} = 5.27$ m/s for $z_{ref} = 60$ m full-scale and $\beta = 0^\circ$ (N-S wind)

Figure 11: Turbulence kinetic energy time-averaged contours from RANS (left) and LES (right) at $z = 0.1$ m (37.5 m full-scale) for $\beta = 0^\circ$ (N-S wind)

4.1.2. Comparison of turbulent kinetic energy field

RANS and LES approaches present greater differences in the k contours, as shown in Figure 11, particularly within the wake regions. As mentioned in subsection 4.1.1, the RANS model's steady formulation suppresses the unsteady vortex shedding and shear-layer roll-up responsible for lateral mixing and wake re-energization, leading to a deficit of resolved turbulent structures near sharp edges. On the other hand, LES preserves intermittent shear-layer detachments that increase k downstream. k contours in Figure 11 indicate that the leading-edge shear layer dominates turbulence production, which explains peak k values in the near wake and at corner regions of buildings. The highest values of k are found after the first row of obstacles and downstream of high-rise buildings, while the downstream location of k peaks is seen to depend on building height and the urban array. In that sense, increases in k propagate downstream, interacting with buildings and canyons. Interestingly, most downstream buildings present negligible fluctuations in the wake compared to those in the lateral separation region. Studies on tandem building configurations attribute it to the influence of first-row obstacles on downstream elements [58]. Barber et al. [10] also noted higher turbulence intensities for the whole range of velocities for a higher density of tall buildings, which can be seen in the Urban Lab region. On the contrary, lower average building height constrains shear development, and together with its high building density, the urban array outside the Urban Lab produces lower local k maxima, although larger and more persistent recirculation.

The large scatter seen in the calibration plot shown in Figure 12 can be attributed to several sources of error. As previously mentioned, the RANS closure systematically damps unsteady shear-layer roll-up and vortex shedding that

produce an underestimation of k . Across many of the high-turbulence field experimental observations, the RANS predictions remain approximately zero. Moreover, although LES captures unsteady structures and resolves most k , its prediction is highly sensitive to the specification of inlet turbulent statistics. In that sense, alterations to the turbulence development upstream of the model, as well as facility and inflow mismatches, such as the turbulent integral length scale, may further amplify these calibration errors [26]. The authors attribute a large part of the error contributions in the k field to differences in the inflow turbulence between CFD and the experiments, although additional analyses are needed to verify this interpretation. These discrepancies may alter local mixing, which ultimately impacts the accuracy of turbulence propagation and flow pattern predictions. Future UAM studies should validate numerical turbulence spectra and integral length scales in the upstream region of the model to ensure a realistic development of turbulent structures, as the lack of current precision in k fields does not allow for confident predictions of UAS flight performance and risk assessments.

4.1.3. Comparison of normalized pressure coefficient

Hereunder, the c_p obtained during IDR experimental campaign are compared against CFD predictions. To unify the results, comparisons include c_p values obtained at 124 common measurement points across the two experimental campaigns. The c_p is calculated using Equation 4.1.3, where p is the measured pressure, and p_{ref} and q_{ref} are the static and dynamic pressures at a reference probe, respectively. For later comparisons between CMT experiments, and due to the difference in the referencing location (refer to subsection 4.2

Figure 12: RANS and LES k comparison against IDR experimental data

Figure 14: Comparison of experimental normalized c_p values between CMT and IDR

759 for more information), the c_p series are normalized by their
760 respective maximum absolute value.

$$c_p = \frac{p - p_{ref}}{q_{ref}} = \frac{p - p_{ref}}{0.5 \rho U_{ref}^2} \quad (7)$$

761 The calibration plot shown in Figure 13 shows that
762 numerical models can accurately predict time-averaged c_p
763 values. The best-fit lines suggest that the mean c_p is less affected
764 by the aforementioned turbulence error. A larger error
765 in the RANS results is also evident in the plot, particularly
766 in the suction regions associated with flow detachment. On
767 the contrary, LES presents a slope much closer to unity and a
768 smaller root-mean-square error, with smaller differences in
769 prediction accuracy across different probe locations.

Figure 13: Normalized c_p calibration plot between IDR experimental data and CFD simulations (RANS and LES)

wind engineering due to its dependence on building geometry and urban wind patterns [26, 60]. In this case, testing the same model in two wind tunnels facilitates a comparison of the c_p values. Because of the elimination of urban-geometric sources of error, the c_p value quantifies the experiment's sensitivity to ABL and laboratory characteristics. The ABL characterization determined that both experiments successfully reproduced the target Eurocode 1 Category III profile despite differences in turbulence generation setups. A similar dimensionless behavior of the ABL in terms of velocity magnitude is seen in Figure 2, with a greater discrepancy in the turbulence intensity profile.

For the IDR tests, a Pitot probe placed on the top of the wind tunnel provided the dynamic pressure used to compute p_{ref} and q_{ref} . The CMT experiments recorded reference variables slightly upstream of the model to avoid wake interference on c_p measurements. The lack of a common reference streamwise location between laboratories causes an offset in c_p values, calculated following Equation 4.1.3. Furthermore, Zhu et al. [26] emphasize that mismatches in the reference streamwise positions in open wind tunnels affect c_p distribution in a single building to a greater extent. In the CMT experiment, variations in static pressure due to ambient atmospheric pressure and the gradual pressure drop along the wind-tunnel flow result in an underestimation of $|c_p|$ in both pressure and suction zones. Hence, to compare pressure results between the two laboratories, the c_p values shown in Figure 14 are normalized to their respective maximum values. This normalization reduces the sensitivity to reference offsets and highlights spatial patterns and relative magnitudes in the pressure distribution.

The calibration plot between pressure coefficient measurements from both wind tunnels for $\beta = 0^\circ$ and $\beta = 180^\circ$ is shown in Figure 14. The strong linear correlation demonstrates good agreement between facilities, confirming that the principal features of the flow, such as separation and recirculation regions, are consistently captured in both

770 4.2. Validation of wind tunnel experiments in two 771 facilities

772 To assess the independence of results from external facility
773 factors, this work compares the c_p values obtained across
774 the two experimental campaigns. Despite the limitations of
775 comparing time-average values of surface pressure against
776 velocity time series measurements, the c_p is usually used in

814 experiments. The agreement across the two facilities in
815 building surface pressure distributions indicates that the
816 local flow is indeed mainly governed by urban geometry.
817 Nonetheless, the most significant deviations from the trend
818 occur in regions of detached flow, where a slight increase in
819 data dispersion is observed for $c_p < 0$. These discrepancies
820 are attributed to the upstream ABL conditioning, which is
821 in turn affected by differences in wind tunnel cross-sections
822 and ABL generation setup. The results suggest that, although
823 absolute pressure values may vary with facility-specific con-
824 ditions, the spatial patterns and relative magnitudes of pres-
825 sure distributions are reproducible across tunnels when the
826 geometry is fixed. It can be inferred that numerical models
827 validated against one experimental test should reproduce
828 the same trends in different facilities, provided that the
829 boundary-layer specifications are matched. Nevertheless, to
830 reduce facility-induced ambiguity, a common referencing is
831 recommended. To avoid the limitations of time-averaged c_p
832 comparisons and increase applicability to UAM, velocity
833 power spectra at multiple heights and integral length scales
834 [26] analyses are also suggested.

835 5. Concluding remarks

836 This paper focuses on the study of experimental and
837 numerical results in urban scenarios, aiming to understand
838 key aerodynamic features that impact applications related
839 to UAM in complex, LiDAR/DTM-derived urban environ-
840 ments. The selected urban model is Benidorm's Urban Lab,
841 an authorized flight area for UAS that enables follow-up
842 studies on UAS operation. Since the current work is oriented
843 towards ensuring the reproducibility of results, the complete
844 methodology is presented so that UAM studies can be repli-
845 cable in different urban scenarios.

846 First, the influence of turbulence modeling on the nu-
847 merical accuracy has been assessed. Both time-averaged
848 velocity and surface pressure fields were captured accu-
849 rately, although some differences were noted between LES
850 and RANS simulations. RANS reproduces the mean flow
851 but systematically underpredicts wake velocities. On the
852 other hand, LES can capture intrinsic unsteady phenom-
853 ena, giving better spatial agreement in average velocity and
854 pressure coefficient (c_p). However, the current numerical
855 setup is not able to predict precise turbulent kinetic energy
856 (k) fields. RANS damps k peaks due to its steady eddy-
857 viscosity closure, and LES results display deviations in ve-
858 locity fluctuations, possibly due to mismatches in turbulent
859 structures development. These errors highlight the need for
860 future UAM studies to conduct more in-depth analyses of
861 velocity and integral length scales in the upstream region
862 of the model, thereby verifying the realistic development
863 of turbulent structures. Results highlight flow detachment
864 near building sharp edges, resulting in strong vorticity re-
865 gions that may hinder safe UAS operations. This behavior is
866 observed to intensify in the high-rise, low-density building
867 array within the Urban Lab, particularly near the first-row
868 buildings. On the contrary, areas with low-rise, dense arrays

869 produced lower local k and mean velocity peaks but higher
870 recirculation regions. Some UAM applications, such as UAS
871 path planning optimization strategies, will likely combine
872 less accurate results with highly accurate LES simulations.

873 This article introduces a novel comparison of c_p dis-
874 tributions in complex urban environments using two wind
875 tunnels. Due to the elimination of geometric uncertainty,
876 discrepancies in the results can be attributed to ABL gen-
877 eration and facility effects, namely, inflow turbulence char-
878 acteristics or test-section cross-section. Despite offsets in
879 the magnitude of c_p values being reported in experiments
880 conducted in the CMT open-circuit tunnel with respect to
881 IDR measurements, primarily caused by variations in the
882 reference pressure location, normalized c_p distributions from
883 both facilities exhibit a high degree of reproducibility. Thus,
884 this confirms that the main flow features are replicated and
885 governed by urban geometric interactions rather than by
886 tunnel-dependent conditions.

887 CRediT authorship contribution statement

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889 Writing – original draft, Conceptualization, Methodology,
890 Investigation, Formal analysis. **Pau Varela:** Writing – re-
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During the preparation of this work, the authors used OpenAI's ChatGPT and Grammarly to assist in improving the clarity, coherence, and readability of various sections of the manuscript. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Data availability

All the data will be available in the following open-access repository: https://zenodo.org/communities/ted_moderat/

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